

Supplementary Information

TG-interacting factor 1 improves risk stratification in patients with NPM1-mutated acute myeloid leukemia

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Supplementary Information 1. The difference analysis results of two groups of continuous variables involved in this study, including Age, WBC, PLT, BM, PB and SCR. (The assumptions test results of Table 1 Supplementary)

A. Description of statistics

Group 1	Group 2	Number	Minimum	Maximum	Median	interquartile	Mean	Standard deviation	Standard Error
Age	TGIF1_high	191	5	85	61	26.5	44.5	18.73	1.355
Age	TGIF1_low	213	2	87	62	24	47	17.8	1.22
WBC	TGIF1_high	167	0.1	427.5	16.66	35.52	4.85	49.29	3.814
WBC	TGIF1_low	180	0.5	261.2	20.8	49.68	6.968	52.53	3.915
PB	TGIF1_high	141	0	98.4	48.6	68	12	33.63	2.832
PB	TGIF1_low	137	0	99.2	40.2	62	10	32.65	2.789
PLT	TGIF1_high	137	4	438	36	44	23	68.98	5.893
PLT	TGIF1_low	156	5	916	39.5	61	22	99.17	7.94
BM	TGIF1_high	138	0	97	70	49.5	35.25	27.92	2.377
BM	TGIF1_low	129	0	98	66	57	29	31.09	2.737
SCR	TGIF1_high	113	0.3	2.11	0.83	0.43	0.6	0.305	0.029
SCR	TGIF1_low	132	0.24	4.22	0.85	0.323	0.69	0.504	0.044

B. Shapiro-Wilk normality test

Group 1	Group 2	Quantity of statistics	p
Age	TGIF1_high	0.9500	0.0000
Age	TGIF1_low	0.9320	0.0000
WBC	TGIF1_high	0.6150	0.0000
WBC	TGIF1_low	0.7260	0.0000
PB	TGIF1_high	0.9050	0.0000
PB	TGIF1_low	0.9110	0.0000
PLT	TGIF1_high	0.6490	0.0000
PLT	TGIF1_low	0.5620	0.0000
BM	TGIF1_high	0.9120	0.0000
BM	TGIF1_low	0.9050	0.0000
SCR	TGIF1_high	0.9580	0.0010
SCR	TGIF1_low	0.7430	0.0000

The results of normality test show that the samples do not meet the normality test ($P < 0.05$), Mann-Whitney U test (Wilcoxon rank sum test) is recommended.

C. Wilcoxon rank sum test

group	Group 1[Number]	Group 2[Number]	Quantity of statistics	The difference	Confidence interval (95%CI)	P values
Age	TGIF1_high [191]	TGIF1_low [214]	19790.0000	1.0000	-7.0000	0.6380
WBC	TGIF1_high [191]	TGIF1_low [214]	13376.5000	3.0220	-8.0200	0.0770
PLT	TGIF1_high [191]	TGIF1_low [214]	10355.5000	2.0000	-14.0000	0.6480
BM	TGIF1_high [191]	TGIF1_low [214]	9360.5000	-2.0000	-12.9000	0.4660
PB	TGIF1_high [191]	TGIF1_low [214]	10493.5000	-4.0000	-14.0000	0.2130
SCR	TGIF1_high [191]	TGIF1_low [214]	6591.5000	0.0600	-0.1600	0.1170

D. Results

In this statistics, there was no statistical significance in age group, WBC group, PLT group, BM group, PB group and SCR group compared with TGIF1_low group and TGIF1_high group. Table 1 shows all the statistical details.

Supplementary Information 2. Cox regression based on Schoenfeld residuals for testing proportional-hazards (PH) assumptions.

Hypothesis testing in Table 2 of this study.

From the output above, the test is not statistically significant for each of the covariates, and the global test is also not statistically significant. Therefore, we can assume the proportional hazards.

Hypothesis testing in Table 3 of this study.

Global Schoenfeld Test p: 0.1436

From the output above, the test is not statistically significant for each of the covariates, and the global test is also not statistically significant. Therefore, we can assume the proportional hazards.

Supplementary Information 3. The R code used in the proportional-hazards (PH) assumption in this study.

```
setwd("XXX")
```

```
library(survival)
```

```
library(survminer)
```

```
library(ggplot2)
```

```
rt=read.table("coxInput.txt",header=T,sep="\t",check.names=F,row.names=1)
```

```
cox <- coxph(Surv(futime, fustat) ~  
Age+gender+FLT3_ITD+NPM1+CBFB_MYH11+RUNX1_RUNX1T1+MLLT3_KMT2  
A+PML_RARA+Risk_Cyto+TGIF1_expression, data = rt)
```

```
ph <- cox.zph(cox)
```

```
ph
```

```
ggcoxzph(ph)
```

Supplementary Information 4. The R code used in the univariate analysis in this study.

```
#install.packages('survival')

setwd("C:\\Users\\lexb4\\Desktop\\uniCox")
library(survival)
rt=read.table("coxInput.txt",header=T,sep="\t",check.names=F,row.names=1)
#rt[, "XX "] = log2(rt[, "XX "] + 1)

outTab=data.frame()
for(i in colnames(rt[,3:ncol(rt)])){
  cox <- coxph(Surv(futime, fustat) ~ rt[,i], data = rt)
  coxSummary = summary(cox)
  coxP=coxSummary$coefficients["Pr(>|z|)"]
  outTab=rbind(outTab,
               cbind(id=i,
                     HR=coxSummary$conf.int["exp(coef)"],
                     HR.95L=coxSummary$conf.int["lower .95"],
                     HR.95H=coxSummary$conf.int["upper .95"],
                     pvalue=coxSummary$coefficients["Pr(>|z|)"]
                    )
               )
}
write.table(outTab,file="uniCox.xls",sep="\t",row.names=F,quote=F)
```

Supplementary Information 5. The R code used in the multivariate analysis in this study.

```
#install.packages('survival')
#install.packages("survminer")
library(survival)
library(survminer)
setwd("C:\\Users\\lexb4\\Desktop\\multiCox")
rt=read.table("coxInput.txt",header=T,sep="\t",check.names=F,row.names=1)
#rt[," XX "] = log2(rt[," XX "] + 1)

multiCox=coxph(Surv(futime, fustat) ~ ., data = rt)
multiCoxSum=summary(multiCox)

outTab=data.frame()
outTab=cbind(
  HR=multiCoxSum$conf.int["exp(coef)"],
  HR.95L=multiCoxSum$conf.int["lower .95"],
  HR.95H=multiCoxSum$conf.int["upper .95"],
  pvalue=multiCoxSum$coefficients["Pr(>|z)"])
outTab=cbind(id=row.names(outTab),outTab)
write.table(outTab,file="multiCox.xls",sep="\t",row.names=F,quote=F)
pdf(file="forest.pdf",
  width = 7,
  height = 6,
  )
ggforest(multiCox,
  main = "Hazard ratio",
  cpositions = c(0.02,0.22, 0.4),
  fontsize = 0.7,
  refLabel = "reference",
  noDigits = 2)
dev.off()
```

Supplementary Information 6. The R code used in the overall survival analysis in this study.

```
#install.packages("survival")
#install.packages("survminer")

library(survival)
library(survminer)
inputFile="input.txt"
outFile="survival.pdf"
var="XXX"
setwd("D:\\biowolf\\bioR\\survivalCutoff")

rt=read.table(inputFile, header=T, sep="\t", check.names=F)
rt=rt[,c("fuptime", "fustat", var)]
colnames(rt)=c("fuptime", "fustat", "var")

res.cut=surv_cutpoint(rt, time = "fuptime", event = "fustat", variables =c("var"))
res.cut
res.cat=surv_categorize(res.cut)
fit=survfit(Surv(fuptime, fustat) ~var, data = res.cat)

diff=survdif(Surv(fuptime, fustat) ~var,data =res.cat)
pValue=1-pchisq(diff$chisq,df=1)
if(pValue<0.001){
  pValue="p<0.001"
}else{
  pValue=paste0("p=",sprintf("%.03f",pValue))
}

surPlot=ggsurvplot(fit,
                   data=res.cat,
```

```
conf.int=TRUE,  
pval=pValue,  
pval.size=5,  
legend.labs=c("High", "Low"),  
legend.title=var,  
xlab="Time(years)",  
break.time.by = 1,  
risk.table.title="",  
palette=c("red", "blue"),  
risk.table=T,  
risk.table.height=.25)  
pdf(file=outFile,onfile = FALSE,width = 6,height =5)  
print(surPlot)  
dev.off()
```

Supplementary Information 7. Event-free survival of AML patients was analyzed from TCGA-AML data.

(A) Effect of ELN2017 risk classification on event-free survival of AML patients. (B) NPM1 mutations and wild-type NPM1 cannot independently predict event-free survival in AML patients (P=0.8257). (C) The event-free survival of NPM1-mutated AML patients were affected by TGIF1 expression. (D) NPM1 mutations combined with TGIF1 do not differentiate event-free survival well.